

Some Aspects of Protoberberine Alkaloids

D. S. BHAKUNI

Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow-226 001

Several protoberberine alkaloids have been isolated from *Corydalis meifolia*, *C. gowaniana*, *Stephania glabra* and *Cocculus pendulus*. The structure and stereochemistry of new bases have been assigned. Biosynthesis, and positive and negative chemical ionization mass spectral studies of some protoberberine alkaloids have been carried out.

SOME twelve years ago in the Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow we initiated a programme of research to investigate the alkaloid bearing Indian plants which either have a reputation as folk medicine or the extract of which show consistent biological activity when screened. The general pattern has been that the alkaloids from such plants are isolated. The structure and stereochemistries are determined. The pharmacological properties of the isolated compounds are studied. Finally, biosynthetic studies are carried out on compounds of biological and chemical interest. Under this programme we have investigated the alkaloids of *Corydalis gowaniana*, *C. meifolia*, *Stephania glabra* and *Cocculus pendulus*. The studies carried out on the protoberberine alkaloids from these plants are reported in the present communication.

Protoberberine alkaloids of *Corydalis gowaniana* : Reinvestigation of the leaves and stems of *C. gowaniana* (Fumariaceae), a perennial herb with bright yellow flowers that grows in the western Himalayas at an altitude of 2500-4000 meters, afforded three new tetrahydroprotoberberines¹, govadine (1), govanine (2) and corygovanine (4), apart from the known phthalideisoquinoline alkaloid, bicuculline. Corlumine, isocorydine, protopine and bicuculline have been isolated earlier from the roots of the plant². The plant had been reported to be efficacious in many ailments³.

- 1 R = R₁ = H
2 R = H; R₁ = Me
3 R = R₁ = Me

Govadine, govanine and corygovanine had in their ir spectra Bohlmann bands at 2800-2700 cm⁻¹ characteristic of a tetrahydroprotoberberine nucleus. This was supported by their uv spectra which had absorption maxima at 210-212 and

280-287 nm typical of tetrahydroprotoberberines⁴. Addition of alkali caused a bathochromic shift to 230-234 and 286-294 nm, respectively in the uv spectra of these bases, thus indicating the presence of phenolic hydroxyl groups.

The nmr spectra of govadine, govanine and corygovanine revealed that these bases had a tetrasubstituted tetrahydroprotoberberine nucleus, since in each case there were only four aromatic protons. The absence of the *ortho*-coupling of the aromatic protons suggested that govadine had substituents at C-2, 3, 10 and 11 positions instead at 2, 3, 9 and 10 positions. The substituents at C-10, 11 instead of C-9, 10 in ring D was also evident by the C-8 methylene protons which appeared as a broad signal centred at δ 3.80. Govadine had only two methoxyl groups. The remaining two oxygen functions in the base were probably present as hydroxyl groups since two protons got exchanged on D₂O shake.

The pattern of the aromatic protons in the nmr spectra of govanine and corygovanine and the absence of A B quartet due to C-8 methylene protons suggested that the substituents in both these bases were also at C-10, 11 positions in ring D and not at C-9, 10 positions. Further, both bases had only one hydroxyl group since only one proton was exchanged in the nmr spectra of these bases on D₂O shake. The presence of monohydroxylic group in the bases was confirmed by acetylation. The nmr spectrum of the bases further revealed the presence of three methoxy function in govanine, whereas one methoxy and one methylenedioxy group were present in corygovanine.

Methylation of govadine with diazomethane gave *O,O*-dimethylgovadine. Under similar conditions govanine afforded *O*-methylgovanine. Both the methyl ethers were found identical in all respects including optical rotation, with (-)-norcoralydine (3) of known absolute configuration⁵. Thus govadine (1) and govanine (2) had the *S*-configuration at the asymmetric carbon atom. Corygovanine on treatment with diazomethane yielded *O*-methyl derivative (5) identical with (\pm)-*O*-methylcorygovanine. Govadine, govanine and corygovanine

had typical mass fragmentation of tetrahydroprotoberberines⁷. Fragmentation occurred with the cracking of ring-C through the retro-Diels-Alder process giving rise to fragments 'a' and 'b'. The fragment 'a' constituted ring-A and B while the fragment 'b' comprised mainly ring-D and the two substituent carbon atoms of ring-C. The substitution pattern in these rings further gave rise to the fragments of the corresponding mass. The ion m/z 176 arising from ion 'a' was common in the mass spectra of govadine, govanine and corygovanine and suggested the presence of one hydroxyl and one methoxy group in ring-A in each of these bases. The ion arising from fragment 'b' was at m/z 164, 150 and 148 in the mass spectra of govanine (2), govadine (1) and corygovanine (4), respectively. This suggested the presence of two methoxyl groups in 2, one methoxyl and one hydroxyl groups in 1, and one methylenedioxy group in 4.

4 R=H
5 R=Me

The structures 1, 2 and 4 for govadine, govanine and corygovanine, respectively were confirmed by their synthesis. Mannich condensation of (\pm) -*O,O*-dibenzyl-*N*-nororientaline using 37% formalin in the presence of glacial acetic acid gave (\pm) -*O,O*-dibenzylgovadine which on hydrogenolysis with ethanolic hydrochloric acid gave (\pm) -govadine. Mannich condensation of (\pm) -*O*-benzyl-*N*-norcodamine in the usual way furnished *O*-benzylgovanine which on treatment with ethanolic hydrochloric acid gave (\pm) -govanine. (+)-Corygovanine was similarly synthesized from 1-(3,4-methylenedioxybenzyl)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-7-benzyloxy-6-methoxyisoquinoline.

Protoberberine alkaloids of *Corydalis meifolia* : *Corydalis* (Papaveraceae), an ornamental genus of about 250 species of perennial herbs with underground tubers are distributed in Europe and Asia. About 25 *Corydalis* species occur in the Himalayan region and Khasi hills in India⁸. *C. meifolia* wall. is one of these species that grows at an altitude, 12000 to 15000 ft. The extracts of various *Corydalis* species are reported to be efficacious in many ailments in the Ayurvedic system of medicine⁹. Ochotensine, an alkaloid that occurs in many *Corydalis* species is reported to stimulate isolated muscles of guinea pig and of rabbit uterus, and induce a fall in blood pressure in anaesthetised cats¹⁰. The plant, however, appeared to have escaped the attention of chemists and pharmacologists.

50% Alcoholic extract of *C. meifolia* when put to a broad biological screen, spasmolytic activity was confirmed in the extract¹¹. In the follow up

studies the activity was concentrated in the alkaloidal fraction of the alcoholic extract. Careful column and preparative thin layer chromatography of the alkaloid mixture on silica gel gave protoberberines, (+)-sinactine (6), apocavidine (8), stylophine (10), (+)-cavidine (7), cheilanthifoline (11), dehydrocavidine (9) and spirobenzylisoquinoline, yenhosmine and protopine. Of the isolated bases dehydrocavidine (9), was a new base. The remaining alkaloids though known were isolated for the first time from *C. meifolia*.

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7 R=Me
8 R=H

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Dehydrocavidine (9) was named so because of its relationship with cavidine. In the uv spectrum of the base the absorption maxima at 347, 372 and 420 nm which remained unchanged in the presence of alkali suggested berberine type of nucleus for the base. The signals for two methoxyl groups were at δ 3.84 and 3.88, respectively and a two-proton signal at δ 6.35 was for methylenedioxy group. A three-proton singlet at δ 2.92 accounted for $C_{13}-CH_3$. The aromatic protons at C-11 and C-12 appeared together as a broad singlet at δ 7.74, one-proton singlets at δ 6.9 and 7.12 were due to aromatic C-1 and C-4 protons, respectively. The C_8-H appeared as singlet at δ 10.4. In the mass spectrum of the base the molecular ion (M^+) was at m/z 350. The other significant ions in the spectrum were at m/z 191, 177 and 145. Sodium borohydride reduction of the base gave a compound identical in all respect with (+)-cavidine (7) except optical rotation.

The alkaloid eluted with benzene from silica gel column was characterized as (+)-cavidine (7) which has been isolated from the tubers of *C. ambigua*¹². (\pm) -Cavidine, named as base-II is also a natural product and had been isolated from *C. ledebouriana*¹³ and *C. thalictrifolia*¹⁴. The conformation of 13-methyltetrahydroprotoberberines has been discussed by Jeffs¹⁵ and it has been concluded that in compounds in which C-13 and C-13a protons are *cis*-to one another, the quinolizine system assumed a *trans*-conformation and C-13 methyl adopts an axial orientation. The compounds of this stereochemistry exhibit Bohlmann's band

in their infra-red spectrum⁴. In the ir spectrum of (+)-cavidine (7) Bohlmann's bands were at 2800-2700 cm^{-1} , confirming thus *trans*-quinolizidine conformation of B/C ring junction. The alkaloid obtained by elution of silica gel column with benzene : ethylacetate (99 : 1) was characterised as apocavidine (8). The base had earlier been isolated from *C. tuberosa*¹⁴. Stereochemistry of apocavidine (8) has been established by converting it into (+)-cavidine (7) of known stereochemistry¹⁵.

Elution of silica gel column with benzene : ethyl acetate (75 : 25) afforded a base, characterised as (+)-sinactine (6). (\pm)- and (-)-sinactine had been isolated from *Sinomenium acutum*¹⁶, *Fumaria species*¹⁷, *Papaver rhoeas*¹⁸ and *Corydalis ambigua*¹⁹. (+)-Sinactine (6), is however, isolated by us for the first time from *C. meifolia*. (+)-Sinactine (6) is a member of tetrahydropyridopyrrolizidine group of alkaloids. The members of this group which show levorotation have been assigned 'S' configuration at the asymmetric centre⁶. (+)-Sinactine (6) exhibits dextrorotation, hence the base must have 'R' configuration at C-13a.

Chromatography of the alkaloidal mixture-H on silica gel column afforded stylophine (10) which was isolated first from *C. tuberosa*²⁰. The base subsequently has been isolated from several *Corydalis species*²¹. A phenolic tetrahydropyridopyrrolizidine alkaloid obtained from the polar chromatographic fractions is identified as cheilanthifoline (11). It was first isolated from *C. scouleri*²². The base subsequently has been isolated from several *Corydalis species*²¹.

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Cavidine (7) and dehydrocavidine (9) isolated from the leaves and stems of *C. meifolia* were tested for spasmolytic activity in isolated guinea pig ileum. The activity of the compounds was assessed by their ability to inhibit the contraction of the smooth muscles induced by various spasmogens, such as acetylcholine, histamine, serotonin and barium chloride. Cavidine (7) exhibited at 10 μg dose 80% and at 50 μg dose 100% spasmolytic activity. Dehydrocavidine (9) exhibited at 10 μg dose 20% and at 50 μg dose 40% spasmolytic activity. The bases nonspecifically blocked the effect of the above mentioned spasmogens in a dose dependent manner. The IC-50 (concentration causing 50% inhibition) against spasmogen was found to be between 0.5 to 1.0 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. As is evident from the results the bases failed to block any of the spasmogens specifically and thus had a nonspecific spasmolytic effect.

Biogenetically the protoberberine alkaloids of *C. meifolia* could be derived in nature from suitably substituted 1-benzyltetrahydroisoquinoline precursors. Tracer experiments have shown that tetrahydropyridopyrrolizidine, scoulerine²³, isocorypalmine²⁴ and canadine²⁴ are converted into the phthalideisoquinoline narcotine. It has been proved firmly that 13-methyltetrahydropyridopyrrolizidine such as corydaline are structural variant of 1-benzyltetrahydroisoquinoline skeleton²⁵.

We have studied the biosynthesis of (+)-cavidine (7). The results of traces experiments are as follows. Initial feeding of (L)-[U-¹⁴C] tyrosine to young plants demonstrated that the plants were actively biosynthesizing cavidine (7). Subsequent feedings of tyrosine in parallel with labelled (\pm)-nor-reticuline, reticuline demonstrated that both were efficient precursors of 7. Feeding of labelled (+)-protosinomenine, nororientaline and norlaudandine showed that none of these were efficiently metabolized by the plant to form 7. The resiospecificity of ¹⁴C label in the biosynthetic cavidine (7) derived from the feeding of (\pm)-[N-¹⁴CH₃] reticuline was established as follows. Labelled cavidine (7) was dehydrogenated with iodine to afford dehydrocavidine (9) with essentially the same molar activity as the parent base. 9 was then treated with phenylmagnesium bromide to give 8-phenyldihydrocavidine with essentially no loss of activity. Kuhn-Roth oxidation of the compound in the usual way furnished radioactive benzoic acid (96% activity of original). Feeding of (\pm)-[1-³H, 3-¹⁴C] nor-reticuline gave labelled cavidine (7). The ¹⁴C : ³H ratio in the precursor was 1 : 9 whereas in biosynthetic 7, 1 : 8. The result thus established that the H atom at the asymmetric centre C-13a in cavidine remains untouched during biotransformation of the norreticuline into cavidine. The regiospecificity of the label in the biosynthetic cavidine (7) derived from (\pm)-[1-³H, 3-¹⁴C] norreticuline was demonstrated as follows. Labelled cavidine (7) was converted into its methiodide and then into its methoxyhydroxide form with essentially no loss of radioactivity. Hofmann degradation of the methoxyhydroxide yielded the methine-I which has essentially the same radioactivity as that of the parent base. The radioactive methine-I was treated with methyl iodide to afford methine methiodide which was passed through amberlite IR-410 anion exchange resin to give the corresponding methoxyhydroxide with essentially the same molar radioactivity as the parent base. Treatment of the methoxyhydroxide with Raney Ni gave the methine-II which was then subjected to second Hofmann degradation in the usual way to give the radioactive methine-III with essentially no loss of radioactivity. Ozonolysis of methine-III furnished the radioactive formaldehyde (dimedone derivative, 90% activity of the original). Feeding of (\pm)-[1-³H, 4'-O-¹⁴CH₃] nor-reticuline gave labelled cavidine (7) which was heated with hydrochloric acid. The liberated radioactive formaldehyde was trapped as formaldehyde-dimethone (98% of the original activity). The results

thus established the methylenedioxy function in ring-D in cavidine (7) is originated from *ortho*-hydroxy-methoxy function, as in other cases. Parallel feedings of (S)–(+), and (R)–(–), reticuline

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lines demonstrated that (R)–(–)– enantiomer was incorporated more efficiently than that of the (S)–(+)-enantiomer. The foregoing tracer experiments thus firmly established that (+)-cavidine (7) is stereospecifically biosynthesised in the plants from (R)–reticuline (12).

Protoberberine alkaloids of *Stephania glabra*: Extracts of the rhizomes of *S. glabra*, a glabrous dextrous climber indigenous to the lower Himalayas (5000-6000 ft) have long been used by the natives as an antidiarrhetic, antipyretic and antiasthmatic²⁶. To date 17 alkaloids have been isolated from the rhizome of the plant. Some of the isolated bases possessed hypotensive and antimicrobial properties. The ethanolic extract of the rhizomes of *S. glabra*, when put to a broad biological screen, showed hypotensive and spasmolytic activities²⁷. In the follow-up studies the activities were found to be concentrated in the alkaloid fraction. This prompted us to reinvestigate the alkaloidal constituents of the plant which resulted in the isolation of several alkaloids²⁸. Of these the isolated protoberberine alkaloids are, capaurine (13), corynoxidine (17), tetrahydropalmatine (14), corydalmine (15) and stepholidine (16), palmatine (18), dehydrocorydalmine (19), jatrorrhizine (20), and stepharanine (21). Most of the alkaloids were known and have been isolated earlier except capaurine (13) and corynoxidine (17), which although known bases, were isolated for the first time from this source.

Capaurine (13) isolated as a minor alkaloid from the chloroform-soluble alkaloid fraction of the ethanolic extract had mass fragmentation pattern characteristic of tetrahydroprotoberberine type of alkaloids. There were two singlet for three protons in the aromatic region. Treatment of the base with an excess of diazomethane yielded *O*-methylcapaurine (13, R₁=OMe). The nmr and other physical data suggested that the compound was *cis*-capaurine.

- 13 R₁=OH; R₂=R₃=Me
 14 R₁=H; R₂=R₃=Me
 15 R₁=R₂=H; R₃=Me
 16 R₁=R₂=R₃=H

Corynoxidine (17), the other minor tetrahydroprotoberberine alkaloid isolated from the chloroform-soluble fraction, was characterized by physical and spectral data as the *N*-oxide of 1-tetrahydropalmatine with a *trans*-B/C ring junction. Corynoxidine has previously been isolated from *Corydalis koidzumiana*²⁹. Perbenzoic acid oxidation of dl-tetrahydropalmatine produced dl-corynoxidine. (–)-Tetrahydropalmatine (14), (–)-corydalmine (15), stepholidine (16) were isolated from the chloroform-soluble alkaloid fraction. The quaternary protoberberine alkaloids palmatine (18), dehydrocorydalmine (19), jatrorrhizine (20), and stepharanine (21) were isolated from the *n*-butanol soluble fraction and were characterized by physical properties, spectroscopic data and direct comparison with an authentic sample.

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There are several reports on the pharmacological properties of the alkaloids of *S. glabra*. Tetrahydropalmatine (14) hydrochloride caused hyperthermia in rats³⁰. Palmatine (18) had been found to possess AcTH-like bactericidal and anticholinesterase effects, and it has been concluded that palmatine (18), dl-tetrahydropalmatine and ergot alkaloids have an analogous pharmacological mechanism. Stepharine (21) has been reported to have antihypertensive properties. Structure-activity relationship has been studied in capaurine (13) for emetine type of activity³¹.

According to biogenetic theory³² the tetrahydroprotoberberine and quaternary protoberberine bases of *S. glabra* could be derived in nature from norlaudanosoline derivatives. Tracer experiments that define the biosynthetic pathways of protoberberine alkaloids of *S. glabra* are as follows. Initial feeding of (L)–[U-¹⁴C] tyrosine demonstrated that the young plants were actively biosynthesising the tetrahydroprotoberberine alkaloids, stepholidine (16), corydalmine (15), tetrahydropalmatine (13) and the quaternary protoberberine alkaloids palmatine (18), dehydrocorydalmine (19), jatrorrhizine (20) and stepharanine (21). In subsequent experiments the labelled hypothetical precursors were fed to the plants. Feeding of tyrosine in parallel with norlaudanosoline, nor-reticuline, reticuline, nororientaline, protosinomenine and norlaudandine demonstrated that norlaudanosoline nor-reticuline and reticuline were the only efficient precursors of protoberberine alkaloids. The regio-specificity of labelling in the biosynthetic stepholidine (16) derived from [3-¹⁴C] nor-reticuline was shown as follows. Labelled stepholidine was treated with diazomethane to afford radioactive

tetrahydropalmatine (14) which was refluxed with methyl iodide to give radioactive tetrahydropalmatine methiodide with essentially no loss of radioactivity. It was then subjected to Hofmann degradation in the usual way to afford the radioactive methine-I which had essentially the same radioactivity as the parent base. Ozonolysis of the radioactive methine-I yielded radioactive formaldehyde trapped as its dimedone derivative (95% of original the activity). Regioselectivity of label in the biosynthetic tetrahydropalmatine and corydalmine derived from [3- 14 C] nor-reticuline were established as above.

- 18 $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = \text{Me}$; $X = \text{NO}_3$
 19 $R_1 = R_2 = \text{Me}$; $R_3 = \text{H}$; $X = \text{Cl}$
 20 $R_1 = R_2 = \text{Me}$; $R_3 = \text{H}$; $X = \text{Cl}$
 21 $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}$; $R_3 = \text{Me}$; $X = \text{Cl}$

Carbon atoms 8 in protoberberine alkaloids were derived from *N*-methyl group of reticuline, was shown as follows. *N*-[14 CH $_3$] Reticuline was fed to young plants and biosynthetic protoberberine alkaloids were isolated. The radioactive tetrahydroprotoberberines were separately dehydrogenated with iodine to furnish corresponding quaternary protoberberines. Each of the radioactive quaternary base was then separately degraded to measure the radioactivity at C-8 as described below in the case of biosynthetic palmatine. Labelled palmatine was treated with phenylmagnesium bromide to give the radioactive 8-phenyldihydropalmatine which on chromic acid oxidation (Kuhn-Roth) afforded radioactive benzoic acid (95% of the original activity). The foregoing experiments established that reticuline is a specific precursor of protoberberines in *S. glabra*. The precursors used, however, were racemic. It would be expected that in the biotransformation only one of the two optical isomers should act as a direct substrate. Parallel feedings with (+)-reticuline and (-)-reticuline demonstrated that stereospecificity is maintained in the bioconversion of 1-benzyl-tetrahydroisoquinoline precursors into protoberberine alkaloids, such as tetrahydropalmatine and palmatine. (+)-Reticuline (12) was incorporated about 70 times more efficiently than the (-)-enantiomer. Feeding experiments demonstrated that protoberberinium salts in nature are formed by dehydrogenation of tetrahydroprotoberberines. The rate of their conversion is, however, very different. In some plants both the tetrahydroprotoberberines and their corresponding quaternary protoberberines coexist, for example in *S. glabra* tetrahydropalmatine (14) and palmatine (18), corydalmine (15) and dehydrocorydalmine; stepholidine (16) and stepharinine (21) are found in the same plant. The quaternary

protoberberines jatrorrhizine, palmatrubine, glabrine and glabrinine also occur in *S. glabra*, however, their corresponding tetrahydroprotoberberines have not yet been isolated.

Tetrahydropalmatine in some plants is found in (+), (-) and (\pm)-forms. Formation of both the enantiomers in the same plant is of considerable biosynthetic interest. We have studied this aspect of biosynthesis of protoberberine alkaloids and the results are as follows. Tracer experiments with dihydroreticuline demonstrated that the compound is specifically incorporated into (+), (-) and (\pm)-tetrahydropalmatines. Feeding of (R)- and (S)-, reticulines separately showed specific incorporation of the enantiomers into (R)- and (S)-, tetrahydropalmatines, respectively. Feeding of [1- 3 H, 4'-O- 14 CH $_3$] reticuline suggested that reticuline is not converted in the plant into dihydroreticuline and racemisation of optically active forms of tetrahydropalmatine does not take place via dehydrotetrahydropalmatine.

Several alkaloids have been isolated by us from the leaves and stems of *Cocculus pendulus*²² (menispermaceae) in the alcoholic extract of which hypotensive and anticancer activities have been confirmed²⁴. Of the isolated bases, the bisbenzylisoquinoline alkaloid, pendulin²⁵ exhibited hypotensive activity, and coculinin²⁶ was found to be an anticancer agent. During the course of detailed investigation of the alkaloid mixture we isolated a new protoberberine alkaloid, (+)-opihocarpinone²⁷. We have assigned the structure and configuration as shown in 22 for (+)-opihocarpinone on the basis of spectroscopic data, chemical transformation and CD measurement. A synthesis of (\pm)-opihocarpinone from berberine has also been achieved.

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Tetrahydroprotoberberine alkaloids, (-)-sinactine and (\pm)-sinactine have been isolated from several plant species²⁸. (+)-Sinactine (6) has been obtained by resolution of (\pm)-sinactine. However, (+)-sinactine (6) as a natural product is isolated for the first time by us from *Corydalis meifolia* Wall²⁹. Based on optical rotation (-)-sinactine was suggested to have S-configuration at carbon 13a. (+)-Sinactine (6) isolated by us from *Corydalis meifolia* on similar reasoning could have R-configuration at the asymmetric centre. We have confirmed that (+)-sinactine indeed has R-configuration²⁸ by biosynthetic technique using labelled (R)-, and (S)-, reticulines and by chemical transformation of (+)-sinactine (6) into (+)-(R)-tetrahydropalmatine (14).

Experiments with labelled 1-benzyltetrahydroisoquinolines and tetrahydroprotoberberine precursors have defined biosynthetic pathways of (+)-sinactine from (R)-reticuline.

In recent years many techniques have been developed to elicit useful and specific information from the mass spectrum of a compound⁴⁰. Chemical ionisation mass spectrometry (CIMS) using ammonia as a reagent gas has emerged as an useful technique because of the softer and selective nature of the ionisation by ammonia⁴¹. Different classes of compounds such as carbohydrates, peptides, steroids, alkaloids and nitrogen containing compounds have been analysed by this technique. Negative chemical ionisation mass spectrometry (NCIMS)⁴² is yet another technique which is gradually gaining acceptance among organic chemists. In order to explore the utility of these techniques in the field of alkaloids, the ammonia CIMS of some tetrahydroprotoberberine alkaloids, coreximine, stepholidine (16), corydalmine (15), tetrahydropalmatine (14), sinactine (6), cavidine (7) and stylopine (10) have been examined by us under both positive and negative ionisation techniques³⁹.

Since alkaloids are sufficiently basic to remove a proton from NH_4^+ , protonated molecular ions give rise to the most intense peaks in the spectra of these compounds. As expected no NH_4^+ adduct ions are observed. The preferred site of protonation will be the nitrogen atom of the quinolizidine system. Protoberberines which have hydroxylic function show loss of H_2O from the $(\text{M}^+-\text{H})^+$ ions, presumably protonated on the hydroxyl oxygen. The other peaks in the spectra of the tetrahydroprotoberberines corresponded to retro-Diels-Alder fragments. In the negative chemical ionisation mass spectrometry the reactant gas can have three functions, (i) showing down the primary high energy electrons to give thermal electrons, (ii) charge transfer when the electron affinity of the reactant gas is less than that of the substance, and (iii) true chemical ionization where ionization occurs as a result of ion molecular reaction. The first two processes lead to resonance electron capture with or without dissociation of the molecule. The use of gases, such as CH_4 , $i\text{-C}_4\text{H}_{10}$, NH_3 and H_2 results in the formation of low energy electrons. $(\text{M}-\text{H})^-$ ion is usually observed when NH_3 is used as the enhancement gas. None of the tetrahydroprotoberberine alkaloids when subjected to NCI gives stable molecular anions. This is understandable as these molecules do not contain any electron capturing groups. However, all the compounds show $(\text{M}-\text{H})^-$ ions presumably formed by dissociative electron capture. Tetrahydroprotoberberine alkaloids containing hydroxyl function give very intense $(\text{M}-\text{H})^-$ ions (83-56%). Loss of the phenolic hydrogen will be relatively easy as it results in the formation of resonance stabilised phenoxide anion. The results of positive and negative chemical ionisation mass spectra of tetrahydroprotoberberine alkaloids using ammonia as the reagent gas show the complementary nature of positive and negative ion mass spectra.

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